
Towards a Living Labs research agenda

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Abstract: This paper proposes a research agenda for Living Labs as after 20 years of Living Lab-practice, theory building is not up to par with the steady growth and expansion of practice in terms of topics, sectors and sheer number of practitioners and initiatives. By means of a literature review, a workshop with the Living Lab research community (N=60) and a self-assessment of Living Labs on key topics (N=70) we were able to identify the following main action points to be tackled by future Living Lab research: 1. Linking the different levels of Living Labs to existing theories and literature streams; 2. Approaches to increase impact, value creation & scaling of Living Labs; 3. Harmonization & differentiation of Living Labs; 4. Long(er)-term user & stakeholder involvement; 5. Inclusive involvement. Especially in terms of impact, there is a big demand from practitioners' perspective which could be addressed by first emphasizing the harmonisation process of the different Living Labs elements and terminology and subsequently theorising and conceptualising the current diversity in terms of themes and topics.

Keywords: Living Labs; Research Agenda; Innovation Management; Open Innovation; User Innovation; Urban Living Labs; Campus Living Labs; Rural Living Labs; Agroecology Living Labs; Methods & Tools.

1 Introduction

Both Living Lab research and practice have thrived during the past two decades, with 2006 seen as a defining moment for the Living Labs movement as symbolised by the birth of the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL). Since that moment there has been steadily increasing attention for Living Labs, as evidenced by academic publications as well as so-called 'grey literature' and policy document from local, regional, national and supra-national institutions like the European Union. As an example to show the current level of interest, Living Labs are explicitly mentioned in 17 different call texts for the 2025 Horizon Europe programme and this number is very likely to increase in the future (ENoLL, 2025). Furthermore, the VITALISE project, which focuses on opening Living Lab infrastructures for external research, was recognized as the best practice in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) integration within Horizon 2020, highlighting the importance of Living Labs in European policymaking (European Commission, 2023). This focus aims to strengthen the social sciences and humanities (SSH) aspects of Living Lab development, ensuring that innovations align with ethical considerations, societal inclusion, user empowerment, and participatory principles central to Living Labs.

On the one hand, over these two decades, Living Labs practice, scope and activities have expanded and evolved, while certain foundational principles have also converged, creating a shared framework for Living Labs (ENoLL, 2025). They are a means to organise innovation ambitions within a sustainable organisation over time, as well as a methodology with a set of core principles to foster responsible innovation in response to wicked problems, problems which are strongly interlinked, affecting multiple stakeholders and that are regarded as nearly impossible to solve (Head & Alford, 2015). In the remainder of this paper, we will refer to them as 'complex problems' as we believe that Living Labs have the capability and ambition to actually solve these issues.

On the other hand, because of the diverging topics and themes where Living Labs have been connected to or where (attempts of) implementations have taken place, and because

of the attention this has generated in terms of academic output as well as other publications, Living Labs as a concept has not always been correctly understood. The use of confusing terminology is common among innovation scholars, and a wide variety of collaborative innovation concepts—such as the Living Lab—have been introduced under different names, often with conflicting or overlapping definitions (Santonen, 2021).

When looking at the papers indexed in Google Scholar on “Living Lab” or “Living Labs”, we notice a steady increase since 2006 and an even increased peak from 2022 onwards. However, when looking at papers where Living Labs are the main topic, the curve is way below the total amount of papers mentioning Living Labs. From 2024 onwards, for example, 286 papers had Living Labs as their main topic while 4,360 publications referenced the concept somewhere in the text more broadly. Importantly, 'Living Lab' remains significantly less popular among scholars than 'testbed' or 'citizen science,' with which it is often confused or used interchangeably (Santonen, 2018), despite referring to quite different concepts. This calls for adopting a specific and focused research agenda that clearly sets the direction and ambitions for Living Lab research in order to avoid the misuse of the concept and to increase the quality and impact of the existing and new initiatives.

2 Understanding and development of Living Labs

Living Labs have emerged as dynamic innovation intermediaries. Based on iterative feedback processes, they provide real-life environments for testing and co-creating innovations orchestrating stakeholder networks, aimed at generating sustainable impact and having the ability to play a pivotal role in innovation ecosystems (Fauth et al., 2024). Typically, Living Labs involve all actors from the so-called quadruple helix. This model expands on the triple helix model by incorporating a fourth component: the public, including civil society, community, and the media (Carayannis & Campbell, 2009). This model emphasizes the importance of society's participation in research and innovation

alongside universities, industry, and government.

In their early days, Living Labs were mostly linked to ICT innovation, with emphasis on the European context (Ballon & Schuurman, 2015; Leminen et al., 2017). In the light of these evolutions, the current Testing & Experimentation Facilities for European AI innovations share a lot of common ground with these early Living Labs, where 'ICT innovation' is being replaced by 'AI innovation' (Buocz et al., 2023; Schuurman et al., 2024). These TEFs are supported by the European Commission to foster testing sites for AI innovation, connecting market demand with AI innovators, and reducing the risks based on real-life testing.

Regarding emerging technologies, it seems like the technology 'testbed' has made a return. Living Labs can then be regarded as an extension to these technology testbeds for emerging technologies where they also emphasise the involvement of societal stakeholders like citizens, public sector organisations, non-for-profit organisations etc. These Living Labs expand the focus of pure technical testing to also include broader societal implications and impacts of these technologies. Early Living Labs primarily focused on user-centered design and open innovation, emphasizing the involvement of end-users in the development and testing of new technologies and services (Coorevits et al., 2018). The goal was to create value for all stakeholders through co-creation, where users, researchers, public sector, and industry partners worked together to develop solutions that meet the needs of the end-users (Schuurman, 2015). However, the scope of early LLs was often limited to specific technological innovations, and the engagement of stakeholders was primarily focused on the later stages of the innovation process (Coorevits et al., 2018). Moreover, the technological problems and solutions were often quite generic – similar innovations could have been developed anywhere by anyone, meaning they were not necessarily linked to particular local issues or contexts.

In contrast – but clearly rising up from the foundations laid by these early, general Living Labs that started from a narrow technology-focused point of view – subsequent applications of the Living Labs approach into other sectors were characterized a connection to a physical place, which may be a neighbourhood, a city, a territory, or some other space-bound place. This broader anchoring of the Living Lab in a particular place has important implications for the types of innovation objectives being pursued, the diversity and types of actors with an interest in the outcomes, and the degree of complexity of activities (McPhee et al., 2021). Thus, looking back on the subsequent emergence of a wide variety of seemingly unrelated different types of Living Labs from the original technology-focused model, we may identify the place-based nature of many of these Living Labs as a unifying concept, which can be seen as cousins in the family tree of Living Labs.

In the following sections, we discuss the most common and popular types of current Living Labs, in line with the latest booklet by the European Network of Living Labs giving an update on current Living Lab trends (ENoLL, 2025).

Agricultural and rural Living Labs

Living Labs in rural and agricultural/agri-food contexts are also often aimed at grand societal changes, leading to a focus on sustainability and agriculture-related environmental challenges (e.g., climate change, a transition to agroecology, habitat and biodiversity loss, economic development in rural area) We argue that these grander challenges necessitate a place-based approach, which shapes both the characteristics of the emerging Living Labs and the operational challenges they face in terms of supporting a wider variety of public sector actors and researchers, and greater complexity, measurement, and scientific support

– features they mostly share with urban Living Labs, which are similarly anchored in a geographical context and which inspired the “place-based typology” we draw on in this paper (McPhee et al., 2021; MCPhee & Schwarz, 2024). MCPhee et al. (2021) argue that urban, rural, and agroecosystem Living Labs are part of a typology of “place-based Living Labs”, which are more strongly embedded in a broader geographical/political context than generic Living Labs, which has an influence on the actors that are attracted – notably including leading actors from the public sector. In agricultural and rural settings, these Living Labs emphasise responsible research and innovation (RRI) and have seen a significant increase in activities, large-scale initiatives and funding, and an increasing number of Living Labs receiving certification from ENoLL. They are further supported by specific policy actions, international networks, and summits.

Urban Living Labs

Another popular type of Living Labs is also linked to the public sector, which may similarly reflect its place-based nature (McPhee et al., 2021). Typically, a public organisation sets up a Living Lab for issues and problems related to one or more policy domains. The most common type within this category is the Urban Living Lab. This can be regarded as complementary with the ‘Smart City’ concept which takes a more technology-driven nature, whereas Urban Living Labs adopt more bottom-up and citizen-centric approaches. In some cases, Smart City initiatives act as foundation for the establishment of Urban Living Labs. Compared to Living Labs for Grand Societal Challenges, which are targeting more global problems and topics, Urban Living Labs are specifically constructed to tackle localised challenges of the areas they serve. In quite some cases, the term Urban Living Lab is used to describe project-based, real-life urban interventions. While these interventions often generate positive results and share many of the defining characteristics of Living Labs, they may lack the organisational framework that ensures the sustainability and scalability of their outcomes.

Inclusive Social Innovation Living Labs

Living Labs emphasizing Inclusive Social Innovation focus on main themes such as social inclusion, community resilience, ecological transitions, and equitable economic development and, on a broader scale, Sustainable Development Goals and their updated versions such as the UN Pact for the Future and the related Digital Compact. The stakeholder ecosystem for these Living Labs often includes NGOs, community groups, public sector organizations, social science researchers, vulnerable citizens, artists, and creative practitioners. Incorporating art and artists is very common in these Living Labs in order to nurture creativity, spark innovative solutions, and promote fresh ways of thinking. By merging artistic expression with participatory processes, these Living Labs foster inclusive spaces that empower communities and engage diverse audiences. Key operational areas for these Living Labs include social inclusion, participatory governance, culture, and cultural heritage. These initiatives aim to build stronger, more resilient communities and address systemic inequalities through innovative approaches.

When operating in an urban context with a local focus, this kind of Living Lab can also be considered a subgroup of Urban Living Labs. However, what is particular, is that these Living Labs address complex societal challenges by creating open, participatory environments where diverse voices can inform both problem framing and solution development (Laborgne et al., 2021). Stakeholder ecosystems often extend beyond traditional actors to include civil society organizations, artists, community groups, and socially engaged researchers. While this inclusive orientation aligns with frameworks like

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) (Von Schomberg, 2013) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Living Lab literature has yet to fully explore how such approaches affect impact, governance, and long-term transformation. Further research is needed to understand the mechanisms through which Living Labs can foster sustained inclusion and social change (Habibipour, 2024).

Campus Living Labs

Campus Living Labs (CLLs) represent a prominent form of Living Labs situated within higher education institutions (HEIs), such as universities, colleges, and technology research institutes. They are defined as systems for innovation and learning where students, academic, and operational staff co-produce knowledge through real-life experimentation and applied research, aiming to embed sustainability across institutional processes while addressing the needs of the ‘campusian’; those who live, study, or work on campus (Stuckrath et al., 2025). CLLs take on diverse forms, which can be categorised into four co-production modes: educational (Favaloro et al., 2019), test-bed (Ribeiro et al., 2020), strategic (Martek et al., 2022), and grassroots (Verheyen et al., 2023). However, somewhat similar to a lot of Urban Living Lab initiatives, most CLLs remain fragmented, short-term projects facing recurring internal challenges around coordination, governance, and unclear structures, as well as external tensions between operational units and academic systems (Herth et al., 2024). Despite the availability of numerous theoretical frameworks, handbooks, and guidelines for implementing Living Labs within HEIs (Evans et al., 2017; Rivera & Savage, 2020; Save et al., 2021; Verhoef & Bossert, 2019), there remains a lack of coherence among these tools, as well as insufficient empirical validation of their effectiveness in real-world settings. Additionally, existing studies rarely document CLL’s day work, such as their methodologies, experiments, including occasional failures and institutional barriers. Future research should prioritise comparative, empirically grounded studies that critically examine how CLLs are initiated, structured, and scaled across diverse HEI contexts. This includes systematically evaluating existing tools and frameworks and openly documenting both successful practices and common pitfalls. Such work is essential to move beyond single-CLL initiatives to more iterative, constructive and successful initiatives.

Referring back to the place-based categorization, we would include the Campus Living Lab to this ‘place-based’ category when the campus itself is a central asset and experimentation environment for the CLL.

Living Lab Harmonization

Next to thematic and local context or place, which are linked to the organisational, strategic level of a Living Lab, there is also a substantial body of literature exploring how Living Labs have been used to develop services across various contexts (e.g., Nesti, 2018; Akasaka et al., 2020; Lehmann et al., 2015), which can be situated at the project and activities level. Only a limited number of studies examine the specific services and methods employed within Living Labs (Dutilleul et al., 2010; Santonen et al., 2024a; Santonen et al., 2024b). Some research has sought to identify the technical devices utilized by Living Labs in the health and well-being sector, yet a broader perspective across different domains remains absent. Living Labs are generally understood to follow an iterative, multi-stage innovation process (Petsani et al. 2024). However, there is no clear consensus among scholars and practitioners regarding the exact stages or their number (Arnkil et al., 2010;

Bergvall-Kåreborn, 2009; Feurstein et al., 2008; Rits et al., 2015; Georges et al., 2015; Schuurman et al., 2016; Coorevits et al., 2018). Furthermore, empirical research on the management and performance of Living Labs is still scarce (Paskaleva & Cooper, 2021). In summary, we argue that a deeper understanding is needed of the key services, tools, methods, devices, processes, assessment frameworks, business models, and governance strategies adopted by Living Labs. Only by systematically analyzing what Living Labs do, how they function, and measuring their impact empirically can we better identify operational challenges and factors contributing to their effectiveness.

3 Research questions & methodology

Research question

The aim of this paper is to propose a general research agenda for Living Labs researchers. In later stages, this research agenda should develop into more focused and thematic research roadmaps enabling to realise the full potential of the Living Lab concept and the related principles, enabling responsible and inclusive solutions for complex problems in a variety of sectors and domains.

RQ1: What are the emerging trends and critical topics that researchers across the diverse fields of Living Labs need to consider for advancing within their respective domains?

RQ2: What key questions must be answered to bridge the gap between the potential of Living Labs as an innovation concept and their real-world impact?

Research design

As a first major step to answer these research questions, we conducted a participatory, bottom-up workshop with the research community during the latest edition of the Open Living Lab Days in Timisoara, Romania. We were able to gather more than 60 participants from all over the world in a face-to-face setting, split over five main topical tables linked to the five conference tracks:

- Living Labs for Grand Societal Challenges (health and wellbeing, climate change, energy and transport, agriculture, natural resources,...)
- Living Labs for Policies, Governance, Collaboration, and Innovation Ecosystems
- Living Labs for Inclusive Soci(et)al Engagement
- Living Labs for Business and Emerging Technology
- Living Labs Operations, Methods, Tools, and Impacts

Each table was moderated by a dedicated facilitator and captured the expert opinions of this diverse group of Living Lab researchers regarding the state-of-the-art of current Living Labs research and on their vision for the future. We ended the workshop by asking how the European Network of Living Labs could support Living Lab researchers in order to realise these future ambitions. Next to this bottom-up approach, involving Living Lab researchers in setting the scope and direction of a research agenda, we also conducted ten in-depth interviews with key profiles in the Living Lab movement connected to the European Network of Living Labs to gather additional input.

We collected all the notes and transcriptions from the moderators and from the interviewees and followed the thematic analysis process (Clarke & Braun, 2014):

- 1 Familiarising ourself with the data;

- 2 Generating initial codes identifying important features of the data relevant to answering the research question(s);
- 3 Searching for themes;
- 4 Reviewing themes;
- 5 Defining and naming themes;
- 6 Reporting on the themes and writing a summarizing narrative.

As a second step we used a sample of 76 completed self-assessments by Living Lab managers based on the standardized evaluation framework developed by ENoLL ([Vervoort et al., 2022](#)) and the harmonized assessment method and KPIs ([Vervoort et al., 2024](#)) for evaluating Living Labs. This self-assessment evaluates the maturity of Living Labs via a [quantitative survey](#) by surveying looking at six main building blocks, fifteen criteria, and thirty-four general KPIs of Living Labs.

The table below provides an overview of these building blocks, criteria and KPIs:

<i>Chapter</i>	<i>Criteria</i>
<i>Strategy</i>	Governance Business Model Culture & Collaboration
<i>Operations</i>	Human Resources Operations
<i>Openness</i>	Equipment & Infrastructure Innovation partnerships, projects & processes Ownership of results
<i>Users & reality</i>	User centricity Lifecycle & real-life Tools & methods
<i>Value & Impact</i>	(Co-created) values Impact(s)
<i>Stability & Harmonization</i>	Stability Harmonization & scale-up

These results can give insights into the current shortcomings as experienced and reported by Living Lab practitioners.

4 Findings

Co-creative workshop and interviews

By means of the thematic analysis, we were able to abstract five recurring topics out of the workshop and interview data. These topics provide an answers to the questions which topics are currently emerging in the Living Lab research community and which answers are still needed to advance the field.

1. LINKING THE DIFFERENT LIVING LABS LEVELS TO EXISTING THEORIES & LITERATURE STREAMS

More research effort and output should be dedicated to linking Living Labs to existing and established theories and literature streams. This includes Open Innovation, User Innovation and Responsible Innovation for Living Labs in general, but especially for the more specific domain-related or context-related Living Labs, other theories and frameworks can be used. Moreover, the links between the three levels of a Living Lab should be further explored and conceptualized as this is a very important and distinctive characteristic of Living Labs. Most research focuses only on one particular level at a time, and this is mostly the Living Lab project. In general, based on interviews with key ENoLL stakeholders and decision makers, most focus should be directed to the organisational level of Living Labs, or at least also takes the relation to this layer into account.

2. APPROACHES TO INCREASE IMPACT, VALUE CREATION & SCALING OF LIVING LABS

More than ever, the importance of clearly demonstrating impact, added value and scaling of Living Labs (on the three levels – long-term organizational, medium-term project and short-term user & stakeholder activities) is put forward. This also links to the challenge of the sustainability of Living Lab approaches, which coincides with the organisational level of a Living Lab. This calls for more research into the different Living Lab business models, which is in its turn closely linked to stakeholder value capture and value creation in Living Labs. Another linked topic is scaling of Living Lab activities, Living Lab outcomes and Living Lab solutions.

3. HARMONIZATION & DIFFERENTIATION OF LIVING LABS

A central paradox in the Living Lab landscape lies in the tension between the search for shared characteristics—such as terminology and approaches—and the inherent diversity of Living Labs in terms of context, topic, and activity. To avoid ‘labwashing’ (using the Living Lab label for only loosely related practices) and to enable comparative research, some level of harmonisation—especially of terminology—is necessary. However, this should not lead to rigid standardisation. The core strength of Living Labs lies in their ability to contextualise both problems and solutions, adapting to evolving local ecosystems and stakeholder dynamics. Therefore, while increasing differentiation can help maximise impact, it must be underpinned by basic harmonisation.

4. LONG(ER)-TERM USER & STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT

This is a recurring topic within Living Lab operations and links mostly with the project level: how to keep stakeholders and users motivated to contribute over a longer period of

time? This links up with more practical topics such as panel and stakeholder management, but is also linked to more established disciplines such as user innovation, lead user theory, psychology, and even economic theories.

5. INCLUSIVE INVOLVEMENT

Partly linked to enduring engagement, the question on inclusivity of involved stakeholders and users is also more relevant than ever. How to be truly inclusive? How to reach more vulnerable populations and profiles? How to avoid losing their voice and contribution in innovation processes? And how to design truly inclusive solutions? And finally, how to operationalize LL activities in line with responsible research and innovation (RRI) principles to be ethical?

Self-assessment survey ENoLL

Since January 2024, 76 Living Labs completed the quantitative self-assessment survey online, 41 non-ENoLL members and 35 ENoLL members. The table below shows the average of all the 76 Living Labs in relation to the six main building blocks.

<i>Living Lab building block</i>	<i>Average overall</i>
Strategy	61,1
Operations	58,2
Openness	57,4
Users & Reality	68,1
Value & Impact	39,8
Stability & harmonization	46,0

Based on these data, practitioners seem to struggle most with value and impact of their Living Lab projects and activities. A stable and more harmonized way of operating Living Labs, which can be linked to their financial sustainability and to the transferability of approaches and outcomes, also scores below 50.

To get a more detailed insight into the different elements comprising these general building blocks, we abstracted the table below reporting the average self-reporting scores in relation to the fifteen criteria (N=76).

<i>Living Lab criterion</i>	<i>Average overall</i>
Governance	57,3
Business Model	69,7

Culture & Collaboration	57,6
Human Resources	53,5
Operations (projects)	46,5
Equipment & infrastructure	76,8
Innovation partnerships & processes	63,3
Ownership of results	40,4
User-centricity	72,4
Lifecycle & real-life	59,7
Tools & methods	71,5
Co-created values	47,2
Impact	26,6
Stability	46,5
Scale-up & harmonization	43,5

In general, impact of the Living Lab projects and activities is regarded as the lowest. Ownership of results can be linked to the multi-stakeholder nature of Living Labs resulting in complex IP regulations. Operations of projects and co-created values also score below 50, and the same goes for stability and scale-up and harmonization.

5 Discussion & conclusion

This paper contributes to the evolving field of Living Labs research by putting forward five concrete elements for a future research agenda. This is necessary as Living Labs as a concept are being used more and more in academic as well as other literature and call texts, with the body of knowledge not following this rate of growth. After a literature review, indicating the current trends and topics of Living Labs, we conducted a workshop with 60 researchers from the Living Lab community and complemented this with 10 interviews with key figures from the European Network of Living Labs. Next to these qualitative data, on which we conducted a thematic analysis, we also gathered 76 responses of Living Lab managers in which they did an online self-assessment of the maturity and strength of 15 items linked to 6 main topics. This multi-method design allows us to formulate an answer to the first research question: What are the emerging trends and critical topics that researchers across the diverse fields of Living Labs need to consider for advancing within their respective domains? Five main research agenda topics emerged out of the qualitative data from the workshop and the interviews:

1. Linking the different levels of Living Labs to existing theories and literature streams
2. Approaches to increase impact, value creation & scaling of Living Labs
3. Harmonization & differentiation of Living Labs
4. Long(er)-term user & stakeholder involvement
5. Inclusive involvement

This first theme emerging out of the qualitative data is not directly reflected in the data of the quantitative self-assessment. However, this should come as no surprise as none of the 15 items relates directly to theories or literature streams. This type of research and conceptualisation might on the contrary help in increasing the currently low scores on project operations, co-created values, stability, impact and scale-up. These elements on the contrary are also present within the other themes emerging from the qualitative data. Especially ‘impact’ receives a significantly lower score by the practitioners, so future research should primarily focus on this type of research, taking into account the peculiar challenges and potential pitfalls as discussed by Paskaleva & Cooper (2021) and Ballon et al. (2018).

We can also draw some conclusions regarding the second research question: What questions must be answered to bridge the gap between the potential of Living Labs as an innovation concept and their real-world impact?

Summarizing, since its inception in the early 2000’s, the Living Labs concept has matured in terms of practice with a wide diversity of Living Lab types becoming increasingly popular. Some common themes across all types are the increasingly more important role of place, context and environment, referred to as ‘place-based Living Labs’. This is the case for rural, agro-ecology, urban and campus Living Labs. This extends the early notion of Living Labs as large-scale pilots for experimentation with new technologies to a more localized and contextualized approach to Living Labs starting from (complex) problems instead of (technological) solutions.

Next to the place-aspect, linking to the real-life environment characteristic of Living Labs, Living Labs are increasingly seen as enablers of inclusive and socially oriented innovation, responding to the growing recognition that technological advancement must be paired with social equity (Rizzo et al., 2021). This links up with the defining co-creation element of Living Labs. Recent developments emphasize the importance of involving marginalized, underrepresented, and vulnerable groups in co-creation processes; not merely as participants, but as active contributors to shaping solutions (Kok et al., 2021). This reflects a broader shift toward embedding values such as justice, accessibility, and empowerment into innovation ecosystems, which can also be linked to the literature stream on responsible innovation management.

A final main conclusion, as opposed, but also linked to differentiation, is the process of harmonisation. ENoLL has initiated the harmonisation process by establishing a dedicated working group to reconcile differences and enhance coherence across practices. This effort builds on the framework proposed by the H2020-funded VITALISE project (grant no. 101007990), which includes terminology, governance and business models, research and innovation processes, services, and data collection methods and tools. While many Living Lab definitions have been proposed, very few studies have examined its broader vocabulary (Kehayia et al. 2023). Governance studies mainly focus on Urban Living Labs case studies (Voorwinden et al., 2023; Cantù et al., 2021). Business model items have been identified (Mastelic et al., 2015, Santonen and Julin, 2019), but no clear blueprint for sustainability has emerged. Living Labs are widely seen to follow iterative innovation processes, yet there is little agreement on the specific stages involved (Arnkil et al., 2010; Schuurman et al., 2016). While Living Lab role in service development is well-documented, few studies address the specific service, methods or tools used (Dutilleul et al., 2010; Santonen et al., 2024a, Petsani et al., 2024). In summary, a systematic and

empirical understanding of Living Lab practices is essential for identifying commonalities and distinguishing meaningful forms of diversification. This includes recognising Living Labs for Inclusive Soci(et)al Engagement, where harmonisation supports inclusive, context-sensitive innovation practices while ensuring methodological coherence across diverse settings.

Summarizing, the practical as well as theoretical developments of Living Labs call for more research connecting the dots and laying out the foundations for future initiatives and roadmaps. Therefore, future research should dig deeper into these initial research agenda elements and also connect these to the current diverse and flourishing field of Living Labs. This would foster more structure and alignment, and give Living Lab practitioners more insights and tools on how to develop the currently lower ranking elements within their Living Lab projects and practice. Especially in terms of impact, there is a big demand from practitioners' perspective which could be addressed by first emphasizing the harmonisation process of the different Living Labs elements and terminology and subsequently theorising and conceptualising the current diversity in terms of themes and topics.

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